

Facile activation of Si-H bond by an electrophilic carbene

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Herein, we have explored the chemistry of 1,3-bis(2,6-di-isopropylphenyl)-5,5-dimethyl-4,6-diketopyrimidinyl-2-ylidene (**1**) with various silanes under mild conditions. The oxidative addition of Si-H bond of phenylsilane with DAC **1** affords the compound **2**, which is unambiguously characterized by multinuclear NMR spectroscopy, elemental analysis, and X-ray single crystal diffraction studies. Interestingly, DAC **1** activates silicon hydride bond of chlorosilanes at room temperature and results in the corresponding silylation products.

Keywords: Phenylsilane, chlorosilanes, carbene, small molecules activation.

Introduction

Activation of a strong bond is the key step in the most of the catalytic chemical transformations. Transition metals are well-known to activate small molecules and enthalpically strong bonds. For transition-metal complexes the activation of a bond stems from the interaction between a vacant orbital at the metal and a bonding orbital of the substrate and simultaneous back donation from the filled d orbital of the metal to an antibonding orbital of the substrate. However, it has recently been demonstrated that several nonmetallic systems are capable of activating small molecules due to the presence of the empty *p*-orbital and lone pair of electrons reside on the same non-metallic centers¹. The isolation of a stable crystalline *N*-heterocyclic carbene by Arduengo *et al.* in the year of 1991² led to the enormous utilization of NHCs as ligands for the transition metals as well as organocatalytic transformations³. Later on, Bertrand and co-workers isolated cyclic alkyl amino carbene (*cAACs*) by the replacement of one of the electronegative amino substituents of NHCs by a strong σ -donor alkyl group⁴. The σ -donor and π -acceptor capabilities of different carbenes correlate with the energy of the HOMO and the LUMO⁵. *cAACs* have smaller HOMO-LUMO gap than NHCs which was utilized for a variety of small molecules activation such as H₂⁶, CO⁷, NH₃⁶, and P₄⁸ and cleavage of a series of E-H bonds (E = Si, B, P)⁹⁻¹³.

Very recently, the strategic incorporation of carbonyl groups into an *N*-heterocyclic carbene (NHCs) scaffold via rapid and high-yielding methodologies afforded a stable and relatively electrophilic diamidocarbenes (DACs)¹⁴. DACs underwent a variety of transformations with a broad range of small molecules including the unprecedented reversible coupling of carbon monoxide, irreversible coupling with isocyanides, metal-free transfer hydrogenations, formal [2+1] cycloadditions, activation of ammonia and insertion into the B-H and P-H bond¹⁴⁻¹⁹. However, the chemistry of the DACs (Dipp) with silanes have not been yet explored. Due to the presence of the C=O groups, the DACs display an enhanced electrophilicity when compared to that of the NHCs and have resulted in the realization of many new types of transformations. Due to our current interest in small molecule activation with compounds with main group elements²⁰⁻²² and their capitalization in homogeneous catalysis²³⁻²⁷, we investigated the reactions of various compounds having Si-H bonds with *N,N'*-diamidocarbene.

Results and discussion

The chemistry of DAC carbene with 2,6-isopropylphenyl (Dipp) substituent is not well explored presumably due to the difficulties associated with the isolation of the pure solid compound at room temperature. It has been observed that when DAC carbene with Dipp substituents (**1**) was heated at 50°C

for 30 h, it underwent an intramolecular C-H activation by the insertion of one of the isopropyl CH moiety of Dipp substituents¹⁸. Nonetheless, when PhSiH₃ was added to the toluene solution of **1**, it led to the formation of compound **2** by oxidative addition of the Si-H bond at the carbene carbon center (Scheme 1).

Scheme 1. Reaction of **1** with phenylsilane.

2 was crystallized in triclinic space group *P*-1 and the selected bond lengths and angles are given in the legend of the Fig. 1²⁰. **2** exhibits an approximate tetrahedral geometry at the carbon atom whereas the carbon atom is flanked by two nitrogen atoms. The C-Si bond is 1.938(8) Å in length, which is comparable to the previously reported Si-C single bonds²¹. The C-H bond length is 0.99(2) Å. The average Si-H bond length is of 1.395 Å, which is in good agreement with the previously reported Si-H single bonds²¹.

A resonance at δ 3.81 ppm at the ¹H NMR spectrum of **2** corresponds to the Si-H protons. Another new resonance

Fig. 1. Molecular structure of **2**. Anisotropic displacement parameters are depicted at the 50% probability level. Hydrogen atoms (except H1, and H2 and H3 are bonded to C1 and Si1, respectively) are omitted for clarity. Selected bond distances (Å) and bond angles (deg): C1-H1, 0.99(2); S1-H1, 1.40(2); S1-H2, 1.39(2); C1-Si1, 1.938(3); Si1-C31, 1.865(3); C1-N1, 1.475(3); C1-N2, 1.489(2); N1-C1-N2, 109.2(2); N1-C1-Si1, 113.7(1); N2-C1-Si1, 113.6(1); C1-Si1-C31, 110.8(1).

appeared at δ 6.01 ppm in the ¹H NMR spectrum of **2**, indicating the formation of C-H bond. The appearance of two signals for the isopropyl groups in ¹H (δ 2.81 and 3.59 ppm) as well as ¹³C NMR (25.60 and 30.30 ppm) indicates that they are not equivalent. The four coordination of the Si atom is mirrored at the ²⁹Si NMR spectrum, which shows a resonance at δ -39.01 ppm. The molecular ion peak was observed at *m/z* 569.35 with the highest relative intensity.

Subsequently, we have also tried to investigate the reactions of majority of the available silanes with **1**. The addition of trichlorosilane and dichloromethylsilane with **1** afforded the corresponding silylated adducts **3** and **4** in 91.4 and 93.2%, respectively (Scheme 2). The formation of **3** and **4** can be attributed to the Si-H bond cleavage by carbene with subsequent oxidative addition. All attempts to get single crystals of **3** and **4** were failed and their compositions are corroborated by multinuclear NMR spectroscopy, elemental analysis, and mass spectrometry.

Scheme 2. Reactions of **1** with various silanes.

A new resonances detected at δ 5.76 and 5.67 ppm in the ¹H NMR spectra recorded for **3** and **4**, respectively, are assigned to the hydrogen atom inserted into the carbene center. In **3** and **4**, the methine group of the (NCH(Si)N) moieties appeared in the ¹³C NMR as singlets at δ 74.04 and 72.83 ppm, respectively. This new resonance corresponds to the aliphatic CH proton, and thereby indicating the formation of a silylation adducts. Furthermore, the ²⁹Si NMR spectrum of

3 and **4** exhibit two new signals at δ –10.90 and 12.79 ppm, reflecting the four coordination of the silicon atoms.

No reactions observed between **1** and diphenylsilane or triphenylsilane, even at an elevated temperature and prolonged reaction times. This is perhaps due to the insufficient polarization of the corresponding Si-H bonds and the silicon atoms in diphenylsilane or triphenylsilane may be too sterically congested to facilitate Si-H bond cleavage¹⁷.

Conclusion

In summary, we have examined the reactivity of *N,N'*-diamidocarbene **1** with primary and chlorosilanes under mild conditions. **1** cleaves the Si-H bonds of a range of silicon-containing species and proceed without intramolecular ring expansion, a side reaction often observed for analogous NHCs. The reaction of **1** with phenylsilane affords **2** that was unambiguously characterized by single crystal X-ray diffraction. In addition, the reactions **1** with chlorosilanes have also been investigated and the corresponding products were verified on the basis of multinuclear NMR spectroscopy, elemental analysis, and mass spectroscopy.

Experimental

All manipulations were carried out in an inert atmosphere of argon using standard Schlenk techniques and in argon filled glove box. The solvents especially toluene and hexane were purified by MBRAUN solvent purification system MB SPS-800. Moreover, benzene was dried and distilled over Na/benzophenone mixture prior to use. Other chemical purchased from Sigma Aldrich and TCI Chemicals were used without further purification. The starting material, 1,3-bis(2,6-di-isopropylphenyl)-5,5-dimethyl-4,6-diketopyrimidinyl-2-ylidene was synthesized by using literature procedures¹⁴. ¹H, ¹³C, ²⁹Si and ¹¹B NMR spectra were recorded in CDCl₃ using a Bruker Avance DPX 200, Bruker Avance DPX 400 or a Bruker Avance DPX 500 spectrometer referenced to external SiMe₄, in the case of ¹H, ¹³C, ²⁹Si and ¹¹B NMR. Elemental analysis was performed by CSIR-National Chemical Laboratory, Pune. However, high resolution mass spectra (HRMs) were obtained using a Q Exactive Thermo Scientific.

Compound 2: A solution of 1,3-bis(2,6-di-iso-propylphenyl)-5,5-dimethyl-4,6-diketopyrimidinyl-2-ylidene (**1**) (0.3 g, 0.648 mmol in toluene 10 mL) was added drop by drop to a solution of phenylsilane (0.07 g, 0.648 mmol in

toluene) at ambient conditions, via cannula. After 2 h ¹H NMR spectrum recorded and showed the formation of product. The solvent was removed under reduced pressure and extracted with toluene (15 mL). The solvent was reduced *in vacuo* to 5 mL and stored at –30°C in a freezer for 2 days to obtain colorless crystals of **2**. Yield: 0.340 g (92.2%). Anal. Calcd. for C₃₆H₄₈N₂O₂Si₁: C, 76.01; H, 8.51; N, 4.92. Found: C, 74.35; H, 8.60; N, 4.58; ¹H NMR (400.31 MHz, C₆D₆, 25°C) δ 0.79 (d, 6H, CH(CH₃)₂), 1.16 (d, 6H, CH(CH₃)₂), 1.34 (d, 12H, (CH(CH₃)₂)₂), 1.56 (s, 3H, CH₃), 1.88 (s, 3H, CH₃), 2.81 (septet, 2H, (CH(CH₃)₂)₂), 3.59 (septet, 2H, (CH(CH₃)₂)₂), 3.81 (d, 2H, SiH₂Ph), 6.01 (t, 1H, NCHN), 6.48 (d, 2H, Ar), 6.77–6.94 (m, 5H, Ar), 7.11–7.14 (m, 4H, Ar) ppm; ¹³C NMR (100.67 MHz, C₆D₆, 25°C); δ 21.09, 22.23, 22.88, 23.20, (CH(CH₃)₂)₂, 25.23, 25.60 (NC(CH₃)₂N), 30.30 (CH(CH₃)₂), 48.40 (NC(CH₃)₂N), 64.82 (NCHN), 124.41, 124.83, 127.96, 128.73, 129.91, 130.35, 136.06, 136.70, 147.64, 148.24 (Ar-C), 173.85 (NC(O)) ppm; ²⁹Si {¹H} NMR (79.49 MHz, C₆D₆, 25°C): δ –39.01 (CSiH₂Ph) ppm. HRMS (ESI, *m/z*): Calcd. 568.34, Found: 569.35 [M]⁺.

Compound 3: A solution of 1,3-bis(2,6-di-iso-propylphenyl)-5,5-dimethyl-4,6-diketopyrimidinyl-2-ylidene (**1**) (0.3 g, 0.648 mmol in toluene 10 mL) was added drop by drop to a solution of trichlorosilane (0.06 g, 0.47 mmol in toluene) at ambient conditions, via cannula. After 2 h ¹H NMR spectrum recorded and showed the formation of product. The solution was removed under reduced pressure and the obtained colorless solid material submitted for spectroscopic studies which were corroborated the pure product formation. Yield: 0.352 g (91.4%). Anal. Calcd. for C₃₀H₄₁Cl₃N₂O₂Si₁: C, 60.45; H, 6.93; N, 4.70. Found: C, 61.83; H, 7.22; N, 4.54; ¹H NMR (400.31 MHz, C₆D₆, 25°C): δ 1.17 (d, 6H, CH(CH₃)₂), 1.29 (d, 6H, CH(CH₃)₂), 1.38 (d, 12H, (CH(CH₃)₂)₂), 1.78 (s, 3H, CH₃), 1.85 (s, 3H, CH₃), 3.05 (septet, 2H, (CH(CH₃)₂)₂), 3.37 (septet, 2H, (CH(CH₃)₂)₂), 5.76 (s, 1H, NCHN), 7.06–7.24 (m, 6H, Ar) ppm; ¹³C NMR (100.67 MHz, C₆D₆, 25°C): δ 22.75, 24.21, 24.51, 25.91 (CH(CH₃)₂)₂, 26.19, 29.55 (NC(CH₃)₂N), 30.29 (CH(CH₃)₂), 47.07 (NC(CH₃)₂N), 74.04 (NCHN), 125.0, 125.612, 130.53, 135.37, 146.36, 149.85 (Ar-C), 171.70 (NC(O)) ppm; ²⁹Si {¹H} NMR (79.49 MHz, C₆D₆, 25°C): δ –10.90 (CSiCl₃) ppm. HRMS (ESI, *m/z*): Calcd. 596.10, Found: 596.19 [M]⁺.

Compound 4: A solution of 1,3-bis(2,6-di-iso-propylphenyl)-5,5-dimethyl-4,6-diketopyrimidinyl-2-ylidene (**1**) (0.2 g, 0.47 mmol in toluene 10 mL) was added drop by drop

to a solution of dichloromethylsilane (0.06 g, 0.47 mmol in toluene) at ambient conditions, via cannula. After 2 h ^1H NMR spectrum recorded and showed the formation of product. The solution was removed under reduced pressure and the obtained colorless solid material submitted for spectroscopic studies which were corroborated the pure product formation. Yield: 0.347 g (93.2%). Anal. Calcd. for $\text{C}_{31}\text{H}_{44}\text{Cl}_2\text{N}_2\text{O}_2\text{Si}_1$: C, 64.68; H, 7.70; N, 4.87. Found: C, 63.47; H, 7.76; N, 4.60; ^1H NMR (400.31 MHz, C_6D_6 , 25°C) δ -0.23 (s, 3H, SiCH_3), 1.20 (d, 6H, $\text{CH}(\text{CH}_3)_2$), 1.29 (d, 6H, $\text{CH}(\text{CH}_3)_2$), 1.42 (d, 12H, $(\text{CH}(\text{CH}_3)_2)_2$), 1.80 (s, 3H, CH_3), 1.92 (s, 3H, CH_3), 3.03 (septet, 2H, $(\text{CH}(\text{CH}_3)_2)_2$), 3.55 (septet, 2H, $(\text{CH}(\text{CH}_3)_2)_2$), 5.67 (s, 1H, NCHN), 7.06–7.22 (m, 6H, *Ar*) ppm; ^{13}C NMR (100.67 MHz, C_6D_6 , 25°C); δ 8.24 (SiCH_3), 24.20, 24.39, 25.94 ($\text{CH}(\text{CH}_3)_2$), 26.21, 29.68 ($\text{NC}(\text{CH}_3)_2\text{N}$), 30.36 ($\text{CH}(\text{CH}_3)_2$), 47.10 ($\text{NC}(\text{CH}_3)_2\text{N}$), 72.83 (NCHN), 125.07, 125.51, 130.46, 135.80, 147.06, 149.78 (*Ar-C*), 172.31 ($\text{NC}(\text{O})$) ppm; ^{29}Si $\{^1\text{H}\}$ NMR (79.49 MHz, C_6D_6 , 25°C): δ 12.79 (CSiCl_3) ppm. HRMS (ESI, *m/z*): Calcd. 575.69, Found for $\text{C}_{31}\text{H}_{45}\text{Cl}_{37}\text{ClN}_2\text{O}_2\text{Si}_1$: 577.25 [$\text{M}+\text{H}$] $^+$.

Crystallographic data for 2: X-Ray intensity data measurements of compound **2** was carried out on a Bruker SMART APEX II CCD diffractometer with graphite-monochromatized ($\text{MoK}\alpha = 0.71073 \text{ \AA}$) radiation. The X-ray generator was operated at 50 kV and 30 mA. A preliminary set of cell constants and an orientation matrix were calculated from three sets of 36 frames. Data were collected with ω scan width of 0.5° at different settings of φ and 2θ keeping the sample-to-detector distance fixed at 5.00 cm. The X-ray data collection was monitored by APEX2 program (Bruker, 2006). All the data were corrected for Lorentzian, polarization, and absorption effects using SAINT and SADABS programs (Bruker, 2006). SHELX-97 was used for structure solution and full matrix least-squares refinement on *F* 2 . All the hydrogen atoms were placed in geometrically idealized position and constrained to ride on their parent atoms. An ORTEP III view of compound **2** was drawn with 50% probability displacement ellipsoids and H atoms omitted for clarity.

Crystal data for compound 2: $\text{C}_{36}\text{H}_{48}\text{N}_2\text{O}_2\text{Si}_1$, *M* = 568.85, colorless, $0.38 \times 0.28 \times 0.18 \text{ mm}^3$, triclinic, space group '*P*-1', *a* = 10.6068 (5) \AA , *b* = 11.6085 (6) \AA , *c* = 15.0656 (8) \AA , α = 96.880 (3) $^\circ$, β = 103.140 (3) $^\circ$, γ = 111.127 (3) $^\circ$, *V* = 1642.94 (15) \AA^3 , *Z* = 2, *T* = 296(2) K, $2\theta_{\text{max}}$ = 51.68 $^\circ$, *D* $_{\text{calcd}}$. (g cm^{-3}) = 1.150, *F*(000) = 616.0, μ (mm^{-1}) = 0.104, 19019 reflec-

tions collected, 5738 unique reflections ($R_{\text{int}} = 0.0510$), 4205 observed ($I > 2\sigma(I)$) reflections, multi-scan absorption correction, $T_{\text{min}} = 0.966$, $T_{\text{max}} = 0.981$, 393 refined parameters, *S* = 1.021, *R*1 = 0.0541, *wR*2 = 0.1176 (all data *R* = 0.0811, *wR*2 = 0.1176), maximum and minimum residual electron densities; $\Delta\rho_{\text{max}} = 0.410$, $\Delta\rho_{\text{min}} = -0.322$ ($\text{e}\text{\AA}^{-3}$). CCDC no. 1850371.

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